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From Trigger to Glimmer

A twist of a fight, a roar within the knot
They keep the bounty full, then mock you with a single shot
A hunch of light, a twig within the fuse
They hold the dagger into a champ, then praise you in clues

It is a signal without a trace
A million-dime succumbed in a pile of hush
It is a quirk with a haste
A counterfeit adorned in a bash

Quite a mess from a perfectionist view
To dip the knife in a flawed hue
Somewhat blessed from a stubborn pew
To muster the halt in a bruised shoe

Then, like an open fire from a closed freezing sight
A burst of hope rushes from the muted sound
For once, like a shut prone hint from a vulgar alarm
A spectrum of ink flusters from the loud abound

Now, with all the might everyone has
A bond with shame unfolds from a story untold
At a time, their seasons anchored in time stamps
A climb with fame directs from a stage tolled

What used to be the grandest act remains a paragon of lack?
Strangled vast in a threshold
What used to be the lowly demeanor ceases an A list hack?
Swindled few in a fourfold

No holds barred, glimmer in a trigger
A step in bridging power
No gap sparked, trigger in a glimmer
A walk to finding humanity' tower

To remain calm amidst the noise
Yet vigilant to claim what is left without remorse